

Absorbance at 405 NM

Relative content of RSV antigen in BPH on various days after 4-d acquisition feeding.

of RSV antigen was indicated as absorbance at 405 nm.

A significant amount of RSV was detected in extracts soon after feeding on RSV-infected plants stopped. Two days later, however, RSV was not detected in 1st-instar nymphs and was at low level in 3d-instar nymphs (see figure). RSV content increased gradually up to 6 d and then declined.

Results showed that RSV acquired by BPH retains antigenicity for 2 d and begins to multiply about 6 d after acquisition feeding begins. □

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Distribution of rice ragged stunt virus (RSV) in infected TN1 plants

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We evaluated distribution of RSV-infected TN1 plants. Thirty-day-old TN1 plants infected with RSV at seedling stage were removed from pots. The roots were thoroughly cleaned, and the plants were divided into roots, leaf sheaths, and leaf blades. The parts of each plant were homogenized in mass with 4 times a phosphate-buffered saline solution (pH 7.4) containing 0.05% Tween 20. A relative amount of RSV antigen was determined through enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) using a polystyrene micro-titre plate (Linbro) coated with 2.5 µg/ml of immunoglobulin against RSV. The enzyme-immunoglobulin conjugate was diluted 300 times. The virus amount was indicated as absorbance at 405 nm in a Micro-ELISA reader. In another test, the leaves and sheaths were numbered based on the tiller number and leaf position from older to younger, and were separately tested in ELISA following the same procedure.

Virus antigen was detected in roots, sheaths, and leaves, but there was more in sheaths than in roots and leaves (Table 1). Regardless of tiller number, the second and third sheaths had higher mean absorbance value than other plant parts (Table 2). RSV was also detected in the

Table 1. Relative amount of RSV in roots, sheath, and leaf blade of TN1 plants 1 mo after inoculation, revealed as absorbance at 405 nm in ELISA. ^a

Sample	Trial	Absorbance		
		Root	Sheath	Leaf
Infected	I ^b	0.40 ± 0.13 ^c	0.49 ± 0.14	0.45 ± 0.07
	II ^d	0.65 ± 0.26	0.73 ± 0.60	0.45 ± 0.07
Healthy		0.07 ± 0.03	0.015 ± 0.01	0.03 ± 0.01

^aExtract at 1/5 dilution was tested directly in ELISA. ^bMean absorbance value from 4 individual infected plants. ^cStandard deviation at 5% level. ^dMean absorbance value from 9 individual infected plants.

Table 2. Distribution of RSV in infected TN1 plants 1 mo after inoculation, revealed as absorbance at 405 nm in ELISA. ^a

Sample	Samples (no.)	Absorbance	
		Range	Mean ^b
First tiller			
Root	9	0.35 - 1.29	0.65 ± 0.27
Sheath 1	9	0.13 - 1.30	0.65 ± 0.34
Sheath 2	9	0.12 - 1.19	0.76 ± 0.36
Sheath 3	8	0.52 - 1.10	0.78 ± 0.24
Sheath 4	7	0.50 - 1.05	0.73 ± 0.18
Sheath 5	3	0.30 - 0.91	0.62 ± 0.25
Leaf 1	8	0.08 - 0.52	0.32 ± 0.16
Leaf 2	8	0.15 - 0.97	0.41 ± 0.25
Leaf 3	8	0.31 - 1.14	0.56 ± 0.29
Leaf 4	6	0.17 - 0.88	0.51 ± 0.21
Leaf 5	3	0.38 - 0.72	0.59 ± 0.15
Youngest leaf sheath	3	0.35 - 1.42	0.71 ± 0.50
Second tiller			
Sheath 1	7	0.40 - 0.88	0.63 ± 0.19
Sheath 2	7	0.34 - 1.47	0.63 ± 0.43
Sheath 3	5	0.32 - 0.91	0.62 ± 0.21
Sheath 4	3	0.39 - 0.50	0.43 ± 0.05
Leaf 1	7	0.06 - 0.75	0.37 ± 0.23
Leaf 2	7	0.14 - 0.48	0.34 ± 0.11
Leaf 3	5	0.32 - 0.83	0.52 ± 0.16
Leaf 4	3	0.33 - 0.45	0.40 ± 0.05

^a Extract at 1/5 dilution was tested directly in ELISA. ^b Standard deviation at 5% level. Mean absorbance of healthy plant root = 0.075 ± 0.25, sheath = 0.015 ± .005, and leaf = 0.026 ± .009.

youngest leaf and sheath, which did not have visible disease symptoms. However,

no RSV was detected in the oldest leaves of some samples. □